

DEVELOPMENT OF THE PEDAGOGICAL FIELD IN UZBEKISTAN DURING THE SECOND HALF OF THE XX CENTURY

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Annotation: The main objective of this article is to study the pedagogical ideas formed in Uzbekistan during the second half of the XX century and their development through scientific research methods.

Keywords: idea, transformation, national, knowledge, methodology

During the second half of the XX century, significant changes took place in the pedagogical field in Uzbekistan. During this period, the education system, teaching methods, and pedagogical theories underwent serious transformations, which positively influenced the overall development of society.

During the second half of the XX century, the pedagogical field in Uzbekistan developed primarily in the following main directions:

1. Renewal of education based on national knowledge and culture.

During the second half of the XX century in Uzbekistan, the pedagogical field developed in important directions such as the renewal of education based on national knowledge and culture. This process mainly involved adapting the education system to national values and integrating the rich heritage of Uzbek culture into the educational process. The main aspects of defining this process include:

- Recognition of national identity: Renewal of education based on national knowledge and culture pays special attention to teaching national history and culture in educational programs. This ensures a deeper understanding of national identity among Uzbek youth and fosters their appreciation of global cultures.

- Modernization of teaching methods: In the Uzbekistan education system, efforts have been made to improve the quality of education by introducing modern pedagogical technologies and teaching methods. This also contributed to promoting scientific and technological progress in educational institutions.

- Comprehensive guidance: Integrating national and global contexts in the educational process provided students with the opportunity to explore various cultural and scientific perspectives. This approach facilitated the development of students' critical thinking skills while preserving national values based on global knowledge.

Overall, these processes have led to significant changes and innovations in Uzbekistan's pedagogical field, contributing to the overall improvement and effectiveness of the education system.

2. Modernization of educational content and enhancement of teaching methodology.

During the second half of the XX century in Uzbekistan, the pedagogical field developed in two important directions: modernization of educational content and enhancement of teaching methodology. These processes can be analyzed as follows:

- Modernization of educational content: Modernizing the education content in Uzbekistan involved expanding educational programs with new subjects and courses that incorporate scientific and technological advancements. This was done to equip students with knowledge and skills that respond to the demands of modern society. Additionally, this process aimed to strengthen national and global scientific collaborations.

- Enhancement of teaching methodology: Improving teaching methodology involved updating teaching methods and introducing interactive approaches, including practical exercises, group work, and discussions. This approach aimed to deepen students' understanding of subjects and enhance their independent thinking skills. Moreover, this process aimed to prepare teachers to utilize new pedagogical technologies and enhance their professional competence. These two main directions are seen as part of the overall efforts to improve the quality and effectiveness of Uzbekistan's education system. Modernization of educational content and enhancement of teaching methodology are strategic steps taken to ensure that students can meet the complex and changing demands of modern society. These changes not only improve the level of education but also contribute to the quality of the teaching process.

3. Enhancement of teacher competencies and elevation of their social status.

During the second half of the XX century in Uzbekistan, the pedagogical field developed in several important directions, particularly in enhancing teacher competencies and elevating their social status. This development was one of the key factors in the overall progress.

During this period, efforts were made to enhance the competencies of teachers through systematic measures aimed at strengthening their professional knowledge and skills. These measures included various training courses, seminars, and scientific-practical conferences. Additionally, incentives were provided to encourage material and moral support for teachers, and efforts were made to elevate their social status.

The development of the pedagogical field in Uzbekistan during the XX century was closely related to the socio-economic and cultural needs of society. Pedagogical ideas were developed, taking into account the socio-economic and cultural requirements of society, which contributed to the improvement of the education system's effectiveness.

References:

1. Karimov, I. (2005). History of the Renewal of Uzbek Education. Tashkent: Ma'rifat.
2. Azimov, A. (2003). Pages from the History of National Knowledge. Tashkent: Sharq.
3. Yusupov, M. (1999). Modern Trends in Teaching Methodology. Tashkent: O'qituvchi.
4. Sobirov, F. (2002). Theoretical Foundations of Teacher Training. Tashkent: University.